

An Overview of Internal Labour Migration In India With Special Reference To Kerala

The basic reason for migration is lack of employment, prevalence of under-employment and intermittent employment which work as push factors. The recruitment system through contractors and their agents is exploitative. These manifest in the inhuman working and living conditions and acquiescence by the migrants of the terms and conditions of employment as they do not have any option, however violative of law these may be.

-National Commission on Rural Labour

ABSTRACT

India continues to experience inter-State migration as a result of complex socioeconomic factors. The freedom of movement for citizens inside this enormous nation state, India, facilitates extensive interstate labor migration. However, this internal mobility of labor inside India offers tremendous opportunity for learning important new information and is yet mostly understudied. This article especially investigates the motivations of these migrants and the role of social networks in the creation of such migration streams, with a focus on migrant construction workers from West Bengal traveling to Kerala. According to a field study in Kerala, the state's proximity to the Gulf and rapid demographic change have significantly reduced the local labor pool, which has increased immigration from other Indian states due to improved job prospects, higher incomes, and efficient payment methods.

CHAPTER ONE INTRODUCTION

Migration is a global phenomenon revealing the nature of the people in search of better life and living condition caused by economic, social, political, cultural, environmental, health and educational factors, affecting both the origin and destination. The Migrant workers. According to International Labor organization Convention no.189 and International Organization for migration, any persons “moving to another country or region to better their material or social conditions and improve the prospect for themselves or their family.” According to the United Nations Department of Economic and Social Affairs/Population Division (2013) International Migration Report, 232 million people live outside their countries of birth. In the coming decades, demographic forces, globalization, and climate changes will increase migration pressures both within and across borders. (Saif Muhammed, 2014).

In India labor is migratory in character in all the aspects, which is the dynamic factor in the dismal scenario of Kerala in the present period. The migration of labor occupies greater significance in the Indian economy, which a thought emerged from unequal development where the people from 'backward region' moved to 'developed regions'.

❖ **An over-view on internal migration in India:** The magnitude of internal migration is far greater than the international migration in a labor intensive country like India, where there is enormous human capital contributing abundantly for economic prosperity, social cohesion and cultural diversity. Our country being the seventh largest of the world in geographical terms and second largest in terms of population is been the major contributor of human capital across the world. But the abundant labor population of the country is unevenly distributed resulting scarcity and abundance across different areas which are to an extent corrected through the process of migration. In order to correct the problem of unemployment and labor shortage this migratory flow have to be promoted to the maximum enabling economic development, social welfare and urban-rural diversification.

Even though the migration process seems to be inevitable as well as essential component for the overall survival, absence of coherent policy frameworks and strategies adopted for migration makes it not fruitful for both origin and destination. Heavy cost incurred in the human development caused by poor labor arrangements and working conditions, obstacles faced during migration, the problems of food, education and health care facilities transfer the migration process to curse than praise. Further worsen the demography as well as the healthy habitat of the destination.

❖ **An overview of inter-state migration to Kerala:** In-migration of the workers to Kerala has a long history. But the recent migration is different in terms of the profile of the migrants, occupation they are engaged in and the magnitude of inflow. The migration in 1980's and 1990's was primarily from the neighboring states like Tamil Nadu and Karnataka but now the laborers from the states as far as West Bengal, Orissa, Bihar, Assam, Uttar Pradesh now flock to Kerala. The activities they are engaged in also got much diversified than earlier.

On examining the migration trend of Kerala, Kerala is now in a threshold of transition and the consequences of large-scale internal migration to the state which play an important role in framing states future. In the past decades there have been a remarkable flow of labors from other states to Kerala. The economic and social imbalances among the states in India is cause for this huge internal migration in general. Increasing literacy rate by better educational sector and deficiency of unskilled job force and International migration to Gulf and European countries created a huge gap in the Kerala's unskilled labor market even though the state is one with high unemployment rate (educated unemployment 7%) in the country. Along with this the decreasing population growth rate further intensified the situation (-8.44 %). Ageing population combined with youth migration to abroad bound to increase labor shortage.

The linguistic, social and cultural differences between the state of origin and Kerala and the large distance the migrants have to travel to reach Kerala makes the inter-state migration more similar to International migration. The geographical differences between states in India particularly between North, North east and south India is comparable to different countries in Asia. Moreover in many cases the distance for inter migration is larger than the crossing of international borders. Kerala is located far off from North, North-East India, the distance to Kochi in Kerala to Kolkata in West Bengal is about 2360km people from Assam have to travel about 3500km to reach Kerala, which is similar to the distance Keralites clear to migrate to Dubai or Abu Dhabi in West Asia.

The differentials in wage rate, Kerala received attention of workers in other states. Migration of workers seeking employment in Kerala from other States like West Bengal, Bihar, Orissa etc. Apart from this workers from neighboring state like Tamil Nadu is increasing but are not paid up to the domestic workers of the state. The contract system of employment is also increasing in the state and they began to move into Kerala and to take work, especially in the construction sectors. What started as trickle soon assumed the dimension of a torrent in the course of a few years. Thus started the era of replacement of migration to Kerala. (Economic Review.2016)

High minimum wage along with improved living condition in Kerala is the main motivating factor for other state workers, the wages are often double or even more than three or four times higher than their home states. For any unskilled work in Kerala the average wage is Rs.500 per day were the national average seems to Rs.187. In the states like West Bengal, Bihar, Assam and Orissa are provided even lower than the national average. Being the highest wage provider of the country, Kerala is called as 'Gulf of other state migrants' as Gulf was Once and still place of fortune for Keralites. Apart from all this reasons the wage differences between domestic and migrant labors have become an attracting force for the local residents to hire migrant labors for the households rather than domestic workers paved way for the emergence of 'daily wage labor market' of migrant labors.

It is important to understand the different waves of migration from Kerala and how much each of these pattern influence the states social, political and economic sustenance. Which predominantly raise up the issue firstly the socio-cultural shift due to migration, economic and social consequences of remittances based economy and the political consequences of the migration.

As per the 68th report by NSSO Kerala's contribution of working force is comparatively very less. The study also figured out that around 11.6 % of migrants who had gone back to their states are reluctant and have not returned to Kerala. The main reason is addressed as the hurdles that they undergo day by day. Migrant laborers are often made to work high risky jobs like that on Quarries and mines.

According to Helen I Safa, the idea that people of necessity are permanently located in one national entity, that the distribution of the world's population is complete forever, and only temporary anomalies now occur are also being challenged. It would be curious outcomes if the size and composition of the labor force of each country was exactly optimal, requiring no exchanges. In practices, world economic integration continually increases rates of mobility, so that in future it is going to be as difficult internationally to give a unequivocal answer to the question 'where are you from'? As it already in developed countries (Safa, 1975). This presently viewed in Kerala equifying all the migrants' workers as 'bhais'. 'bengalees'..bihariess so on.

A Report Commissioned by GIFT(Gulati Institute of Finance and Taxation) under Kerala state Finance Department in 2013 submitted to Labor and Rehabilitation Department Government Of Kerala says that there more than one million DML (Domestic Migrant Labors) in Kerala across different sectors annually remitting 17,500 crore rupees which is equivalent to 4% of Kerala GDP. It is estimated that 2.35 lakh non-Keralites arrive in Kerala every year. Currently the number estimated in total is 25 lakhs in an age proportion 18-35, with an average wage from 300-500 daily.

With the sign of rapid growth of Kerala economy and the increased activities particularly infrastructure and construction sectors the in-migration is expected to grow faster in coming years. Apart from its importance in the economic development of the state, interstate migration flow facilitate retaining the demographic balance in a state which has the highest proportion of the aged population and were a good proportion of the population in working age group have migrated out of the state.

❖ **Daily labor market:** A labor market can be defined as an adjustment mechanism which balances the supply of and demand for labor (Prמוד Verma, 1987). It can be represented as an interaction of demand and supplies of various categories of labor through which wage rate is determined. A local labor market is usually surrounded in urban cities, where the common participants are workers and employers. The main function of these labor market is to match workers and job by fixing the remuneration in a way acceptable for both. Existence of an efficient labor market is vital for the sustainable growth of the economy which solve the problem of unemployment to an extent by the demand and supply mechanism with existing population.

➤ *Motivation*

One of the greatest threats and challenges associate with labour migration is the effect that migration has the bargaining power of local labour. Whether the worker comes from the other side of the globe or the other side of the country, when she/he enters the local labour force and is willing to work at a lower wage and/or under less regulated conditions, it forces the local work force –organized or not –to respond (Moses and Rajan ,2012).

Migration related employment and life is has become a major issue of discussion in India since 1970s. Started from a large-scale migration to North America and Europe by the advent of industrialization and technicalistion, making our country presently the highest remittance receiving nation of the world.

On analyzing different studies related to migration in India and Kerala in specific, most of the studies have been done on international migration focusing mainly on Gulf migration. Most of the migration studies focused on skilled and semi-skilled migrants from Kerala to different parts of the country and Gulf. For instance the migration of Malayalee nurses to the capital city since 1980s and 1990s which further paved way for international migrations. Very nominal studies have been carried out in the field of internal migration focusing specifically on in and out migration from and to Kerala. Also while reading and reviewing several newspaper articles, journals and research papers it is been noticed that presently the huge other state migration to the low skilled sectors of the state (Kerala) is becoming a need as well as an issue in Kerala recently.

Over the past decades there was an abundant flow of labors from other states especially West Bengal, Bihar, Assam, Orissa along with North Eastern regions of the countries and people from Nepal and illegal Bangladeshi migrants as Bengalis, with fake Indian ID cards are migrating to the state in large. Better wage and life is the soul motive behind this migration. But this large scale migration is leading to social, economic and cultural transformation in Kerala, at the same time this migrant have now become an inevitable part for the existence of Kerala economy as huge developmental activities are flourishing which opens up the employment opportunities in the unskilled sector of the state.

The study attempts to trace the means and causes for this significant shift causing increased dependency on them by the Kerala community and also to examine different factors motivated this huge flow of migrant community. Analyzing various aspects like wage rates, their social demography, political protections and policies in comparison with domestic workers of the state. The study also attempts to trace the emergence of new migrant daily labor market in the urban cities of the state.

The study focus on the migrant community in detail considering all the socio-economic and demographic factors along with the wage differentials. Examining all these factors through primary survey from three major districts of Kerala with highest number of in-migrants. Till the date the Domestic migrant Labor report by GIFT (Gulati Institute of Finance and Taxation) under the Finance department of Government of Kerala was the prominent study in this field of internal migration through a train survey but had omitted different aspects of this migration. Through this study I attempt to trace the present migration trend in Kerala in low skilled sectors and the emergence of a new system of 'Daily Migrant labor market in Kerala' which is recent trend viewed in Kerala over the past years.

➤ *The Literature Reviews*

There are number of studies pertaining the topic migration resulting to the flow of remittance and thereby implications in both origin and destination. On discussing on migration we generally discuss on International migration which have brought about a drastic change in Country as the largest remittance receiving nation and Kerala being placed at the top among the state with 40%. Many studies have been conducted in this regards especially to Gulf countries. But the studies on internal migration from Kerala and to Kerala are few. In this part, review of literatures includes various studies related to internal migration in India in general and Kerala in Specific, related to Social, Economic and cultural implications. Initially analyzing the concept of migration and its trend in general, then nationally and then focusing on different dimensions of internal migration Locally to Kerala in specific.

Tapan and Majumdar (1969) discuss the nature and socio-economic characteristics of inter- state migrants based on 1961 census. The study is only based on urban areas were the climate, social outlook, educational level, the economic gains and the temperaments were the induced factors for migration. Along with this the paper also discuss the problems created by the inter migration like inflationary pressure due to rise aggregate demand and the social discriminations and how the inter-state migrations contributed for the economic development of the areas and the social, environmental and economic pressure created by the same.

Krishnan (1991) examines the wage structure and wage movements and their relation employment and output in the agrarian economy. It developed a concept of interrelated labor market where it is divided into four sections, relation with agriculture-construction sector, rural urban transition but estimating vector auto regressions and testing the casual relationship among the different wage rates. The paper also emphasis on the importance of social norms in labor market behavior, movements in the wage relatives in relation to the changes in the product demand and also develop a analytical model to explain employment behavior in interrelated labor market to explain the changes in the output and employment in the agrarian sector of Kerala economy.

Singh (1992) attempted to review most of the studies undertaken in the field of migration in India. The paper is review of different published till 1990's on migration and its different characteristics with greater focus on immobility, the social and demographic consequences of migration on sending and receiving communities along with the social, economic and demographic behavior of the migrants. The review separately discuss every aspects of migration like data on migration, international and internal migration, volume and stream of migration its causes and consequences opening up the way for the means and ways for further research in the field of migration.

Gosh and Sharma (1995) emphasizes on the migration pattern on rural Bihar. In this paper a survey result of 56 sample villages spread over six districts have mentions that there is lowest incidence migration in better agriculture areas and highest incidence of migration in better agriculture areas and highest incidence of migration in the opposite environment. They migrate to Punjab, West Bengal, Delhi, Assam and Kerala for their job. Temporary migrants out migrate for a particular or specified period. The author also points out the destination and the occupation of migrant workers. Migration of workers generally takes place from areas of low employment to those with high employment. Kerala had too witnessed a large number of migrant workers from Bihar just before the advent of the migrant workers from the north eastern states. The study mainly focuses on the pattern of the aspects of rural migration.

Ravi and Sasikumar (2003) deals with both international and internal migration which have a large scale impact on economic growth and reduction in scale of poverty in many parts of India. The paper recommends for changes in government policies with proper improvement in international and internal migration policies and laws. And in the case of International migration they suggest for the maximization of the emigrational tendencies with appropriate institutional and policy measures. They advocated the policies by dividing their suggestions under four categories like improving the synergy between migration and development secondly improving labor market outcomes, thirdly ensuring of basic entitlements to migrant workers and finally improving the social and political environment for migration.

Grimm (2005) pointed out that the migrant workers come to sell his labor power where there is a labor shortage. They admitted to do certain kind of Job. They had no rights, claims or reality outside his filling of the job. While he fills it, they paid and accommodated. It is not men who immigrate but machine minders, sweepers, cement mixers, cleaners etc. This is significance to temporary migration.

Ronald Skeldon (2008) emphasis on migration and development. The paper reviews the minority of migrants, the flow of remittance, the problem of skilled labor (brain drain) and the migration diaspora. It explains on how the current trends and concerns over migration and development with a traditional focus on emigrational studies, its cause and effects on movement of people and the policy designs to protect and promote migrants to inhibit development. The paper put forward the need for research on integration of urbanization, international migration and development and also the reaction of a new socio-economic and political space. And the need for the framing of laws and policies for migrants which have become an integral part of development.

Mathew Kutty (2009) the study was a contrary to the conventional wisdom. Urbanization and migration. High rates of migration (permanent and temporary) into urbanized areas have continued despite rising levels of formal unemployment and persistent poverty. The explanation lies in the expanding urban informal sector which represents a significant pull.

Rashmi Sharma (2011) discuss the crucial features of International migration all over the world in the wake of increasing number of female migrants. The participation of women in low skilled, skilled jobs, and also special concern on female trafficking as an emerging issue is been discussed. Along with it the trends and issues of female migration from India with special attention on emigration from Kerala as nurses and teachers to gulf and other Western countries have been given. The paper call for the need for systematic recording of the female emigrants in specific and urgent need for a gender sensitive migration policy.

Amarnath and Shraddha (2011) reveals the regional heterogeneity decline over period of 1991-2005 i.e.; shifting in food habit from cereals and non-cereals. Along with the shift in the consumption pattern has been discussed. The study is based on cross section data pertaining to household's food consumption expenditure in India from data's from CSO and NSSO. The study mainly focus on state and sector level consumption patterns which are now become unified to an extent by the advent of large scale internal migration since the past decades.

Ajith Kumar (2011) examines the dimension of vulnerability of other state migrant laborers in the sub-national context taking Kerala as the area of study. Analyzing how the host (Kerala) respond to reduce the vulnerability if inter-state migrant laborers and also to make an assessment of a pioneering welfare scheme for the migrant workers, which are introduced by Government of Kerala. The paper points on the portality of entitlements are the lack of rights which they enjoyed before migration and how the state and the Central government have to call for a better coordination among both the origin and destination. It also calls for the strategy to unify the migrants providing and making aware about their rights where the authorities fails to reach to significant segment of migrant population. The study has been conducted through primary data collection technique from migrant workers, state officials, employers/agents/contractors. The paper conclude suggesting for a multi-institutional and multidimensional comprehensive study on the migrant workers population which is a major component of Kerala's employment sector.

Kundu and Sarangi (2012) study based on NSS data 2011 census have established that poor people are less mobile as far as permanent or semi-permanent migration is concerned. The quintiles, rural areas and poor's. The data has limitations as sample of temporary migrants are minimal lacking ideas on their origin and destination.

Kundu and Sarswati (2012) deal on the migration and urbanization patters in recent decades. The study analyze the trend and pattern of migration in Indian using the population census data (1961-2011) and NSS data (1983-2008), carried out in national and state level focusing on the trends and patterns of internal migration, gender and geographical boundaries of movements separately from rural to urban areas. Along with that changing pattern of mobility of migrant workers, Employment structure of migrant adult their social economic characteristics and the overview on urbanization trending the macro level.

Mathai Czaika (2012) analyze the multiple dimensions and factors in internal and international migration, focusing on pattern of migration by analyzing the role of households, capabilities and aspirations of migrants, risk involved and the in temporal income and consumption relative to deprivation. According the study it is revealed that the rural migration is higher

than the urban migration and an intra-state migration is increasing over the past years.

Upadhyaya and Rutten (2012) the paper reviews migration and development, by debating the current flows and reverse flow of migrant resources to India, giving a clear cut understanding of migration and migrants socio-economic implications. The paper is detail discussion in transactional mobility and the development achieved thereby. The study put forward a methodological approach to the flow and reverse flow involved in migration providing an organizational structure, in transactional social fields regulating the flow of migration, which will help to provide a comprehensive understanding of migration and development.

Rajan and Moses (2012) on their study on labor migration and integration in Kerala, made an attempt to show out of state migrants are kept isolated from the surrounding community. From the study it is found that migrant workers to Kerala are unable to integrate with the local workers and community and have no information about the prevailing local wage, their rights, working hours and the amenities provided in the work sites. They opines that the labor union have to be effective and keen in integrating the workers and the locals in Kerala so that their working environment will be safe and secure.

Indrani maumdar, N Neethu et al;(2013) consolidate the meso level migration based on the survey conducted by NSSO between 2007-08 across 20 states regarding the pattern of female labor migration, working condition and heir civic life, providing broad structure of female migration in India. The pear challenges the common assumption of 'Feminization of labor' and its presumed relationship with migration and posits alternatives for approaching gender and migration, labor force and labor laws in India. And analyze how the neo-liberal driven economic growth have narrowed the opportunity for women's work but reinforced entrenched patriarchies.

Keshari and Bhagat (2013) analyses the differentials between temporary and permanent labor migration at state level, using the unit level data of 64th round of NSS data from July 2007 to 30 June 2008 assessing the relationship by considering various socio economic factors. The study has been done on the basis of abridged data sheet by computing Monthly per capita expenditure (MPCE). They observed that if the MPCE quintiles are low then the temporary migration rates are high and based on this observation they said that the temporary migration is predominantly a rural phenomenon that to rural to urban areas. Commonly from northern India with states based on agrarian economy. Even though the study in detail observed the difference between temporary and permanent migration from the point of origin but avoided the migration impact of this migration on the destination, and fail to mention the major migration destinations.

Jayarajan (2013) attempts to solve the research gap on family migration in India were the 'push- pull factors' in family migration by identifying strands of reasons with hypothetical examples. The family migration is discussed by incorporating the complex interplays in it. Besides that the social, Political, development and environmental factors for a comprehensive understanding is done. Emigrational trends is considered in connection with the growth theory and third world urbanization the major factors leading to the spatial mobility of families in India were the number of migrants increased from 1.7 lakhs in 1993 to 3.5 lakhs in 2007-08 s per the study.

Narayana and Venkiteswaran (2013) domestic migrant labor in Kerala is estimated the stock and flows of migrant labors. Even though the unemployment rate hit by 7.4% Kerala is home for 25 lakh migrant workers. The socio-economic characteristics, working and living conditions of migrant workers are studied. As per the study Perumbavoor, a place in Ernakulam district of Kerala has more number of migrant workers in Kerala. As per the studies conducted conducted over there they have made recommendations that they must be provided a unique registration id card and it can be used for availing benefits of all the schemes that the different departments of the state government offers to the domestic migrant laborers. It is suggested that the provision of affordable housing and associated services to migrant workers may be done by the state government through the formation of non-profit organization under section 25 of the Companies Act. They also suggested that the states government undertake awareness programmes among the migrant workers and the employers employing them.

Mathew John (2014) points out that seasonal migration has been a source of income for rural households who are unable to support themselves and the family through agriculture. Household's number diversify their (the migrant worker's) economic activities outside the traditional agriculture sphere to urban areas in the lean period. He points to different demographic and socio-economic factors such as age sex, educational qualification, religion etc. as some causes leading to this temporary migration.

Ahmad (2014) deals with the emerging trends in the Indian economy with the inflow of remittance and the related phenomenon's. The Journal gives an approximate estimation on the countries from which India receives the highest remittance as the top position is for North America followed by Europe and Middle East countries. Whole is divide mainly as three parts as the role of remittance in overall development with special focus on merits of remittances received in the Indian economy, secondly the different phases of migration and finally the domination of Gulf countries in remittance proportion. The journal in detail discussed the flow and role of remittance in and to different sectors but need not discussed the major utilizers' f this remittances and confined it to a statement as macro and micro development rather than specifying it.

Saikia Dilip (2014) the paper examines the characteristics and economic conditions of the migrant workers in Kerala based on a primary survey on 166 workers from Thrivnanthapuram district of Kerala. It analyses the household and demographic details, the reasons for migration, through whom they have migrated, living condition, occupation, and wage income. The nature of employment doesn't seem to have a change but there was a drastic change in the working and living conditions of the migrated communities where they earn three or four times higher wages than their native place. The saving-investment nature of the migrant people is poor but the rate of remittance was quite high as they are very much satisfied with what they are earning from Kerala.

Saikia Dilip (2015) examines the economic condition of the migrant workers in Kerala by analyzing the income, consumption and savings patterns with the nature of the employment, with the help of a primary data of 166 migrant workers from Thivananthapuram district of Kerala. The paper shows the transformation of migrant population in their income and living condition from a low-income bracket to high income bracket with before and after migration by looking on their work and living conditions in Kerala and their native place.

Abbas Rameez (2015) presents a framework for internal migration in India, from the field work conducted in Mumbai and Kolkata arguing that the development factors are alone insufficient for explaining the citizenship outcomes in India. As the citizenship of migrant workers are in a great question of impoverishment. The article defines citizenship and citizenship regimes by examining the relationship between citizenship and development, their legal status, rights and identity and their participation as components of citizenship regimes. This research as a whole shows how internal migration process have justified by more restrictive citizenship regime and how the curtailment of citizenship rights solely be a byproduct of India's development challenges, under the hypothesis that internal migration processes are key to understanding developing countries citizenship regimes, like that in an international migration.

Manoj P.K and Vidya Viswanath (2015) the paper makes an empirical enquiry on the socio-economic conditions of unorganized sector domestic migrant labors (DML) OF Ernakulam district in the central part of Kerala and suggest the strategies for improving the working and living conditions of the migrant laborers of the state.

Joy puthuma (2016) the paper observes the extent of native labor availability in the rural labor market and also to analyses the scope of migrant workers in the current labor market through the secondary data sources, from the three sectors namely agriculture, industrial and service sector. The coming of migrant labors is magnified as a relief for the deficit in the manual labor market of the state as they supply cheap labor force in the labor market. The paper observe decreased gap between the demand and supply of labor especially on agriculture sector, were the sector presently exist because of the availability of migrant labors.

Mohan C Anju (2016) the paper studies the various aspects of inter-state migration in Kerala, by analyzing the existence of high wage and lack of domestic manual labor resulting to a high inflow of migrant workers from different parts of the country. By tracing their social and economic characteristics and also by identifying the factors that determine the standard of living of migrant labors in Kerala, using the linear regression model to determine the standard of living.

Lizy James (2016) study measures the attitude of Migrant workers towards Malayalees from the 300 samples of migrant population and 250 samples from local population from different parts of the Ernakulam district to analyses the extent to which the attitudes and behaviours of the migrant workers towards Malayalee's are influenced by factors like wage they receive, place of origin, relationship with the principal employer and the contractor, their intention to settle in Kerala etc. Along with this this study measures the level at which the migrant workers are integrated to the society, using the two dimensional model of Ethnosizer, categorising the integration level of migrant workers into that of Assimilation, Integration, Marginalisation and Separation; based on commitment of migrant workers to the host state (Kerala and) their commitment to the state of origin. A comparative analysis of the experiences of the Malayalee migrants in other countries with regard to the attitude and behaviour of the local people towards them in the host society; and the attitude and behaviour of Malayalees towards the migrant workers, as experienced by them in their work and living environment, in their host society (Kerala) is also done in this study.

Joy puthuma (2016) attempts to assess the changing structure of rural employment and its implication on rural labor market, with special focus on transformation from farm sectors to non-farm sectors and had observed that there has been a drastic shift in the occupational structure of the country due to the shifts of male workers, which have tightened the urban labor market.

➤ *Research Gap:*

Basically all the studies on migration are focusing on International Migration. But few studies have focused on internal migration and domestic migrant labors. However the studies on internal migration emphasizing on the pattern and determinants of migration is important, which is not carried out or discussed by existing studies. The issues like the sectors employed the nature of employment. Wages provided etc. are important aspects which need further examination.

Hence this study focus on the recent trends, patterns and its various determinants of internal migration To Kerala in link to the emerging daily labor market system and also examines the wage differentials existing between migrant workers and domesticworkers. Research in Kerala migration have been widely studied based on flow of remittance , the social and demography to an extent of both origin and destination. Many migration analyst have given factual description and theoretical aspects of migration but all these studies have confined in International migration mainly. Most of the researchers have shown lesser interest in internal migration studies because of the lack of availability of exact data sources and the difficulties incurred in collection of data on comparing with International migration studies.

➤ *Research Hypothesis And Research Question:*

This study is going to test two important hypotheses (directional hypothesis). Firstly a set of push and pull factors together determine the internal migration to Kerala and Secondly the increase in internal migration is due to high demand for low skilled labors (with relatively high wage as compared to other states). The major research questions that discussed over the study are: What are the patterns of internal migration to Kerala? What are the important determinants determining the large scale in-migration? Does there exist any link between the internal migration and emergence of daily labor market in Kerala? What are the changes viewed socially and economically in Kerala? And finally what is the wage difference existing between migrant and domestic workers?

➤ *Objectives Of The Study:*

To explore the recent pattern of migration to Kerala and its determinants. · To find out the link between in-migration and informal labor market in Kerala. · To study the wage differentials between migrants and non-migrants (domestic workers) and what accounts for it in Kerala.

➤ *Chapter Scheme:*

The first chapter is the Introduction section giving a general profile of internal migration, India and Kerala in specific, followed by the motivation of the study, the literature reviews, Research gap of the study, Research hypothesis and questions and the objectives of the study. The second chapter Titles data and methodology give a detailed profile of the selected districts, the data size and the methodology followed for the data collection. The third chapter has the result and discussion part which is broadly divided into 4 sections namely; Migration pattern, employment and living condition of migrant labors, remittance details and Wage details of Migrants and native labors. The final Chapter titled Findings and conclusion comprises the major findings of the study followed by suggestions and conclusion.

CHAPTER TWO DATA AND METHODOLOGY

❖ *The District Profiles*

➤ *District Profile of Kozhikode in Northern Region*

Kozhikode district is situated on the south west coast of India. The district is bounded on the north by Kannur district, on the east by Wayanad district, on the south by Malappuram district and on the west by the Arabian Sea. Topographically the district has three distinct regions - the sandy, the rocky highlands formed by the hilly portion of the Western Ghats and lateritic midland. Of the total area of 2344 sq.kms., the sandy coastal belt is 362.85 sq.kms., lateritic midlands 1343.50 sq.kms. And rocky highlands 637.65 sq.kms. All the three taluks are spreaded over the three regions. The district has a coastal length of about 80 kms. The highland region accounts for 26.80 per cent and the lowland region for 15.55 per cent of the total area of the district. The Kozhikode district came into existence on 1st January 1957, originally consisting of five taluks, Vadakara, Koyilandy, Kozhikode, Ernad & Tirur. With the formation of malapuram district on 1st june 1969 & Wayandu on 1st November 1980, Kozhikode district now consist of one revenue division, three taluks, twelve blocks, 78 panchayats and 117 villages.

Table 1 District Profile of Kozhikode in Northern Region

Area	2,206sq.km
Population	2,613,683
Literacy	85%

➤ *District Profile of Thrissur in Central Kerala*

Thrissur is the cultural capital of Kerala. Thrissur District is located in the central part of Kerala, derived its name from 'Thri-Shiva-Perur', which literally translates to "The City of Three Siva". (Vadakkum Nathan Temple, Asokeswarm Temple and Iritichira Temple). Sakthan Thampuran, known as the architect of Thrissur Town, introduced many reforms which modernised the city and its glory reached its heights during his period. Thrissur is well-known for its Jewellery business and is called the 'Gold Capital of India'. Thrissur District is divided into six Thaluks which are Thalappilly, Chavakkad, Thrissur, Kodungallur, Mukundapuram and Chalakudy. There are 255 villages and 01 Revenue Dn.in the District. Area: 3032 Sq Km, There are 7 Urban Local Bodies in the District which are:-Chavakkad, Guruvayur, Kumnnamkulam, Chalakudy, Kodungallur, Irinjalakuda Municipalities and Thrissur Corporation.

Table 2 District Profile of Thrissur in Central Kerala

Profile	Urban	Rural
Actual Population	3,110,327	2,974,232
Male	1,474,665	1,422,052
Female	1,635,662	1,552,180
Population Growth	4.58%	8.66%
Area Sq. Km	3,032	3,032
Density/km ²	1,026	981
Proportion to Kerala Population	9.32%	9.34%

➤ *District Profile of Kottayam in Southern Region*

Kottayam District was formed in July 1949. The District name literally means the interior of a fort (Kotta-Akam). Beautiful backwaters, lush paddy fields, rubber plantations and totally literate people have shot Kottayam into fame with a title 'land of letters', lakes and latex. The district is flanked by western that on the east and Vembanad Lake and Kuttanadan paddy field on the west. Located in the South to Central Kerala, Kottayam is bounded on Ernakulam District in the north, Idukki district in the east, on the South by Alappuzha and Pathanamthitta Districts. The District is overlooking Vembanad Lake on the Western side Kottayam lies between Latitude 9 ° 15 and 10° 21 and Longitude 76 ° 22 and 77° 25. Kanjirapally and Meenachil taluk have laterite soil and Vaikom taluk, and various parts of Changanacherry and Kottayam taluk have alluvial soil.35 m above Sea level. Kottayam district consists of two revenue divisions Kottayam and Pala. Kottayam, Changanacherry, Vaikom, Kanjirapally, Meenachil are the five taluks in Kottayam District.

Table 3 District Profile of Kottayam in Southern Region

Area	2203 sq km
Population	1979384
Male	970140
Female	1009244
Density	885persons/Sq.Km.

- *The Methodology of Primary Survey:*

The data have been collected from the primary sources. But to cover the objectives in specific the study intends to use primary data collected using migration survey schedule extensively. The data has been collected from different districts of Kerala dividing us Northern Kerala, Central Kerala and Southern Kerala interviewing both migrant and domestic labors from low skilled sector. Which would be helpful to know the real essence of huge labour migration from different parts of the state to Kerala covering most of the area under production and service sector where the migrant unskilled labor force are dominant.

Table 4 The Methodology

Regions	Districts	% of in migrants in Kerala (2008)	Rank of Districts with the Region	No of Construction site visits	Sample Size (migrant)	Sample Size (Local)	Total Sample	No of respondent did not respond
Northern Kerala	Kasaragod	7.8	5					
	Kannur	17.7	3					
	Wayanad	11.5	4					
	Kozhikode	36.5	1	5	55	16	71	65
	Malappuram	25.1	2					
Central Kerala	Palakkad	31.1	4					
	Thrissur	43.5	1	5	240	69	309	20
	Ernakulam	40.7	2					
	Idukki	36.3	3					
Southern Kerala	Kottayam	43.4	1	5	120	35	155	40
	Alappuzha	33.6	5					
	Pathanamthitta	36.6	4					
	Kollam	38.0	2	15	415	120	535	
	Thiruvananthapuram	37.4	3					
	Kerala Total	33.5						

(NSS migration Survey Report 2007-08)

The table shows the methodology followed for the study. Initially All the 14 districts of Kerala is been divided into three regions as Northern Kerala, Central Kerala an Southern Kerala on the basis of geographical location. From each of the regions district with highest percentage of migrants (in-migrants in Kerala) is selected (based on the NSS survey data, 2007-08). From

Northern Kerala, Kozhikode is chosen with the highest number of in-migrant population say 36.5 percent and from the Central Kerala Thrissur is selected with a percentage of 43.5 likewise Kottayam district is selected from Southern part of the state with a percentage of 43.4 percent.

From each of the district's 5 construction sites were visited at random. Along with the construction sites in-migrant samples have been selected from various manufacturing as well as service sectors of the state. Major sectors from which samples have been selected other than construction sectors are plywood industries, wood-carpentry industries, hotels and restaurants and from the daily wage labors from the local migrant labor market. The data of the samples is collected on the basis of regions, districts, percentage of migrants to Kerala, Number of construction sites visited, Sample size of migrants and non-migrant workers.

From the Kozhikode district the total migrant samples collected were 55 whereas the non migrant workers (domestic workers) is 16 with a total of 71 samples. The Thrissur district have the highest number of both migrants (240) and non-migrants

(69) workers with a total of 309 samples. Kottayam district have the total of 120 migrant samples and 35 non-migrant samples, with a total of 155 samples. As a total there is 415 migrant samples and 120 non-migrant samples comprising give a total of 535 samples on adding up the both.

Fig 1 Political Map of Kerala

The picture shows the political map of Kerala on which the study have been conducted. On the three major districts namely Kozhikode from northern region, Thrissur from central region and Kottayam from southern part which is highly migrant labor populated areas of Kerala based 2007-08 NSS survey.

CHAPTER THREE RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

➤ *Migration Pattern:*

On discussing on any migration trends there will be different push and pull factors.in Kerala the push factors like poverty, population density, unemployment , agricultural failure or low yield , low demand for domestic laborers, low wages, war and disasters, religious and caste issues. Along with it the pull factors like high wages, better employment opportunities, improved living conditions, free health and education factors etc. play the role. In this section of the chapter the various factors determine the migration trends of the labour workers in Kerala is been analyzed.

• *Age Group of Migrant Labours*

The Table (No: 5) and followed figure (No: 2) shows the age categories of the migrant workers to Kerala from other states were 62 percent of the workers are ion the age category of 20-30 followed by a 22 percent in the age group of 30-40 and 10 percent below 20.Below 10 percent are under the age category of 40-50 and above. This shows that the migrant labors are a very young working force.

Table 5 shows the Age-group of Migrant labours

Age group	Frequency	Percent
Below 20 years	42	10
20 to 30 years	248	62
30 to 40 years	89	22
40 to 50 years	23	6
Above 50 years	1	0.25
Total	403	100

(Source: Calculation using primary survey data)

Fig 2 Age Group of Migrant labors

(Source: Table No: 5)

➤ *Caste of the migrant labors*

From the below Shown table (No: 6) and Figure (No: 3) it is evident that OBC (39.4%) is the largest caste followed by SC (27.7%) and others (22.8%). The ST is of very nominal in number with 10% out of the total of 403 migrant samples selected.

Table 6 Shows the Caste of Migrant Labors

Caste	Frequency	Percent
ST	40	9.9
SC	112	27.7
OBC	159	39.4
Others	92	22.8
Total	403	100.00

(Source: Calculation using primary survey data)

Fig 3 Caste of migrant labors
(Source: Table No: 6)

Table 7 Shows The Religion of the Migrant Labors

Religion	Frequency	Percent
Hindu	234	58.06
Muslim	139	34.49
Christian	26	6.45
Others	4	0.99
Total	403	100

(Source: Calculation using primary survey data)

From the above shown Table(No:7) and Figure(No:4) it is observed that among the different religious migrants community from other states of India it is the Hindu community dominates with 58.06% followed by Muslim community (34.49%) and nominal of 6.45% of Christian community and 0.99% of the workers from other religious communities. Interestingly majority of the Muslim community is heading from West Bengal and Bihar which also includes the illegal Bangladesh migrants who come in India illegally in search of job.

Fig 4 Religion of Migrant Labors
(Source: Table No: 3)

Table 8 Shows the Level of Education of Migrant Labors

Education	Frequency	Percent
illiterate	58	14.39
Primary Education	182	45.16
Secondary Education	162	40.2
Above	1	0.25
Total	403	100

(Source: Calculation using primary survey data)

From the table (No:8) and figure it is clear that nearly half of the migrant population say 45.16 % of the people have education up to primary level followed by a 40.2 % of migrant people having secondary education and a 14.39% people who are illiterate. During the survey it is observed that people from Bihar and West Bengal are more illiterate and primarily educated but states nearby Kerala say Tamil Nadu and Karnataka followed by Assam and some parts of the West Bengal have an educational qualification up to secondary level and negligibly low population have the educational qualification above secondary level. From this it can be concluded that the increase in the literacy rate of the Kerala have created a wide employment gap in the low skilled sectors of the Kerala economy.

Fig 5 Educational Level of Migrant Labors
(Source: table No: 4)

➤ *Marital Status of the Migrant Labors*

From the data (Table No: 9 and Fig No: 6) it is observed that about 70.97% of the migrant population are unmarried youth, followed by 28.78% of married. From the survey it is observed that about 98 % of the migrant workers are men and that to under the age of 30 (Table No: 1). Only very few migrants take their family along with them, as their wife’s working along with them or as maids in Kerala, with their children accommodated in the Government schools The regions Of Kerala like Perumbavoor of Ernakulam district and Payipaadu of Kottayam district have other state students admitted as there whole stay up there engaged in different sectors.

Table 9 Shows the Marital Status of Migrant Labors

Marital Status	Frequency	Percent
Unmarried	286	70.97
Married	116	28.78
Widow/Separated	1	0.25
Total	403	100

(Source: Calculation using primary survey data)

Fig 6 Marital Status of Migrant Labors
(Source: Table No: 5)

➤ *Employment And Living Conditions Of The Migrant Labors:*

The following section of the analysis chapter consist of the employment and the living conditions of migrant workers in Kerala, were the large scale migration to Kerala had viewed a downward trend in the social as well as environmental down graveness. The workers from other states usually suffer on lack of proper living and working conditions. On this section major observations and determinants of the living condition of migrant labors are been observed and explained.

The life of the migrant labors is not much easy in Kerala, were a single room is been shared by more than 10 persons, Mostly a whole building will be hired by 0-70 labors probably under one contractor. With little way for hygienic toilets, proper drinking water. Many in turn lives on poor shacks and roofing's on plastic sheets. In many parts especially in urban areas they cook, eat and sleep in the open space.

The Kerala is now increasingly dependent on migrant laborers but the facilities provided to them are often worse than our imagination but the employers reiterate that they are provided with reasonable wage and decent accommodation (While in most of the places and work areas the workers they in small shacks with minimal toilet facilities and clean drinking water).But while considering the wage and regular job the migrant workers say they are happy with what they are provided with. They do not demand better facilities and employers exploit it by extracting them more with less expenditures. It is evident from many places that the migrant community is vulnerable to exploitation because of their plight, lack of awareness and willingness to compromise for a better life. They face the possibility of being sidelined by employers who see them mere 'slaves' who would not standup for their rights.

Table 10 Shows Toilet Facility for the Migrant Labors

Toilet type	Frequency	Percent
Not Responded	3	0.74
Private toilet within house	326	80.89
Public Toilet	38	9.43
No toilet	36	8.93
Total	403	100

(Source: Calculation using primary survey data)

It is observed from the table (No: 10) that about 80.89% of the migrant have toilet facilities in the work place or living area. Whereas nearly 10% percent access the public toilets and other 9% have no toilet facilities where they depend on public areas. This has created huge environmental issues in Kerala as need for the provision of good and proper accommodation should be provided by the employer itself. In most of the areas the accommodation facilities are provided by the employer or contractor itself but the food is been prepared by themselves. On an approximation nearly 20-60 people together live in an area. The huge migration of other state migrants have gave rise to the slums and slum like areas in many parts of Kerala.

Table 11 Shows Drinking Water Facility Aailed for Migrant Labors

Water type	Frequency	percent
Bottled/packed water	1	0.25
Tube wells	74	18.36
Wells/Ponds	240	59.55
Public water sources	88	21.84
Total	403	100

(Source: Calculation using primary survey data)

It is clear from the table (No:11) that the migrant workers have access to safe drinking water were 59.55% of the people have access to wells/ponds 21% depend on public water sources and 18% have tube wells nearby their working areas. During the survey it is observed that every migrant workers opined that pure water and good climate for working as one of the important factor attracted them to Kerala.

➤ *The Accommodation Provided to Migrant Labors*

Most of the in migrant workers from other states were badly affected with poor working conditions as very poor facilities been provided for them in their work place. They are treated as secondary citizens who were promised with good food and accommodation by the contractors before migration. The risky jobs on the construction sites are forcefully done by them like they are meant for it without proper life savers and insurance. The in-migrant population are unaware about their rights to claim. Their illiteracy and language barrier further intensify the situations.

From The Survey it is viewed that the labors from other parts of the country have poor accommodation facilities. As per the labor laws and norms it is the duty of the employer to provide good accommodation facilities to the workers but the facilities provided to them are not satisfactory. From Figure it is observed that 77.17% of the people live in cemented, another 11.91% live in poor house but 9.43% have pakka houses. Most of them living in fully furnished or pakka houses are rented by the workers itself rather than depending on the employer. The contract labors working in the construction sites live in the construction site itself. Where they don't even have the access to safe drinking water and toilet facilities.

Table 12 Shows The Type Of Accommodation Of Migrant Labors

Accommodation	Frequency	Percent
Fully Furnished	4	0.74
Only Pakka	38	9.43
Semi Pakka/ Cemented	311	77.17
Poor	48	11.91
No House	2	0.5
Total	403	100

(Source: Calculation using primary survey data)

Fig 7 Type of Accomodation of Migrant Labors
(Source: Table No: 12)

➤ *The State of Domicile*

The table (No: 13 and figure (No: 8 shows the percentage of labor migrant flow from other states of India. As per the survey West Bengal have the highest number of migrants with 42.18% followed by Assam (17.37%) and Bihar (16.63%). Other states like Assam, Tamil Nadu, and Uttar Pradesh have their proportion in the migrant labor flow. During the primary survey it is observed that there are differential ties in the sectors in which labors are engaged i.e.; workers from Assam are usually engaged in wood and plywood industries, Bihar and West Bengal people are engaged in daily wage jobs and as construction workers, people from North East usually works in hotels restaurants, Up people are engaged in furniture manufacturing and rest are scattered among different semi-skilled sectors of the state. Presently the other state workers are engaged even in the traditional agricultural cultivation due to scarcity of domestic labors.

Table 13 shows the state of domicile of migrant labors

State	Frequency	Percent
Assam	70	17.37
Bihar	67	16.63
Chhattisgarh	1	0.25
M.P	10	2.48
MP	12	2.98
North East	3	0.74
Northeast	2	0.5
Odisha	24	5.96
Tamil Nadu	14	3.47
Uttar Pradesh	15	3.72
West Bengal	170	42.18
Karnataka	1	0.25
Nepal	1	0.25
Odisha	11	2.73
Rajasthan	2	0.5
Total	403	100

(Source: Calculation using primary survey data)

Fig 8 State of Domicile of Migrant Labors
(Source: Table No: 10)

Table 14 Shows The Nature of Employment of Migrant Labors

Nature of employment	Frequency	Percent
Nil	2	0.5
Permanent	3	0.74
Contract	132	32.75
Daily wages	266	66.1
Others	1	0.25
Total	403	100

(Source: Calculation using primary survey data)

Fig 9 Nature of Employment of Migrant Labors
(Source: Table No: 14)

The above table (No: 14) and figure (No: 9) shows the different sectors or nature of the employment in which migrant labors are engaged. More than half say 66.1% of the workers are engaged in daily wage jobs. It clearly defines the emerging ‘migrant daily labor market in Kerala’. 32.75% are engaged in contract jobs, in the initial stages of the migrant labor flow it was through the contractors and agents the labors are been taken from different parts of the country. Very nominal number are engaged in permanent jobs and other related works. Due to mobile characteristics of the migrant workers everywhere they are employed and paid in daily basis. The majority of the migrant labors are illiterate rural population who become the mere preys of exploitation by the contractors and the domestic population. They are hired and employed without following the labor laws and regulations like police station registration, special ID cards, the record of their personnel details and Insurance facilities.

➤ *Remittance Details*

These sections of the chapter analyze and discuss the remittance details which include the channel, mode and amount remitted based on the calculations made from the primary survey. As per the study conducted by GIFT, the migrant labors send an amount of order of 17500 crore rupees annually which comprise nearly 4% of Kerala GDP.

Table 15 Shows Number of Migrant Labors who Remit Money

Remittance	Frequency	Percent
Yes	382	94.79
No	21	5.21
Total	403	100

(Source: Calculation using primary survey data)

The study mainly focus on the migrant money flow to other states from Kerala economy in a year. It is viewed from the primary survey that 94.79% of the migrant workers remit money to their home state while only 5.21% did not show the remittance tendency. But those who are not remitting are either new to Kerala or haven’t saved enough to remit. From the previous studies and government reports it is inferred that approximately 17 thousand crore rupees is been remitted from Kerala to Other parts of the country which comprises 6-7% of the total Kerala GDP.

Table 16 Shows Channel of Remittance by Migrant Labors

Channel remit	No. of observations	Percent
Not responded	22	5.47
banks	95	23.63
Post office	2	0.5
Friends	269	66.92
Self	7	1.74
Others	5	1.24
Total	403	100

(Source: Calculation using primary survey data)

Fig 10 Channel of Remittance by Migrant Workers
(Source: Table No: 16)

The table (No: 8) and figure (No: 8) shows the different channels or means through which the migrants remit the money. About 66.92% of them remit through friends. Maybe one among the 10-20 will be having a bank account or going home then everyone who are coming nearby will give the money, which is then distributes. The migrants who have bank A/c remit through it (22.63%) nominal of nearly 2% remit through self or others say relatives. And 5.47% haven't responded to it.

Table 17 Shows the Remittance Amount by Migrant Labors

Amount remit	No. of observation	Percent
Below 10000	75	18.61
10000-20000	136	33.71
20000-30000	52	13
30000-40000	21	5.12
40000-50000	37	9.12
Above 50000	82	20.3
Total	403	100

(Source: Calculation using primary survey data)

The table (No: 17) and figure (No: 11) shows the amount which migrant labors remit annually. Nearly 33.71% of them remit amount between 10000-20000 followed by 20.3% people remitting above 50000 and 18.6% people remit below 10000. and nearly 10% of people remitting 40000- 50000. From the primary survey it is viewed that every migrant workers remit at least a small amount to their home and many of them remit in every month, were the amount varies from 3000-6000 per month.

Fig 11 Amount Remitted by Migrant Labors

(Source: Table No: 11)

➤ *Wage Details of Migrant and Native Labors:*

In this section of the analysis part wage details regarding both the domestic and migrant workers are calculated and analyzed. Firstly on the basis of the state of domicile, secondly sex, followed by caste and education. The wage disparity is also a major problem faced by the in migrants is that if the domestic workers are paid 700 for daily work in a day for the same work the migrant labor will be provide with 300-400 without food and without specified working time in reality most of the migrant labors are unaware about the labor system prevailing in Kerala.

Exploitation and torturing from the part of contractors or owners who hire them If a migrant labor earn Rs.500 daily out of it Rs.100 is a compulsory payment for the contractor who brought them to Kerala. There will be nearly 50-200 workers under a contractor who provide them to the needy construction sites on the daily basis as well on the contractual basis.

➤ *Daily Wage Statistics of Labors on the Basis of State of Domicile*

From the table (No: 8) it is viewed that the mean wage of a native worker (Keralite) is ₹419.07 whereas of a migrant worker is ₹322.64. The standard deviation (SD) of the Native is 48.02 and SD of migrant is 42.36. Out of the total of 121 native workers and 403 migrant workers surveyed.

Table 18 Shows the Category of Labors Based on State of Domicile

Categories	Daily Wage statistics (in Rs.)		
	Mean	standard deviation	No of Observation
Natives	419.07	48.02	121
migrants	322.64	42.36	403

(Source: Calculation using primary survey data)

Fig 12 Wage Differentials Based on State of Domicile
(Source: Table No: 14)

➤ *Wage Categories on the Basis of Sex of Labors*

The table (No.19) categories the wage differentials among the natives and migrants on the basis of sex/gender. The mean wage earned by a native male worker is ₹ 430.91, with a corresponding SD of 46.68 from 88 observations surveyed. Whereas of a migrant male worker is ₹323.02 with a SD of 41.84 from 401 samples surveyed. From the analysis of the data it has observed that there exist a huge wage gap on the gender basis. The average earning of a native female worker is ₹387.48 with a SD of 36.18 from the total of 33 samples. The size of the female migrant population is negligibly low to 2 samples all over the survey with an average earnings of ₹247.67 with SD of 78.72.it is concluded from the survey analysis that the wage gap on the basis of gender is still high in the low-semi skilled sectors of the economy.

Table 19 Shows the Wage Differentials on the Basis of State of Domicile

Categories		Daily Wage statistics (in Rs.)		
		Mean	Standard deviation	No. of Observation
Male	Natives	430.91	46.68	88
	Migrants	323.02	41.94	401
	Male Total	342.43	59.60	489
Female	Natives	387.48	36.18	33
	Migrants	247.67	78.72	2
	Female Total	379.50	49.98	35

(Source: Calculation using primary survey data)

➤ *Wage Categories Based on the Caste of the Labors*

On analyzing the wage differentials based on the caste of native and migrant workers from table (No.20). The Average wage earned by the ST native worker is ₹ 416.67 with a SD of 23.57 from 2 samples. Whereas that of a migrant worker is ₹317.10 with SD of 36.85 from 40 people surveyed. Similarly the SC category the native mean wage is ₹427.78 and migrant is of ₹ 321.08 with SD of 47.14 & 31.93 correspondingly from 121 samples. Followed by OBC category with ₹409.19 by natives and ₹ 326.71 with SD of 41.77 and 51.57 correspondingly from 220 observations. And the others (the general category) with an average earnings of ₹429.86 (natives) and ₹319.93 (migrants) with SD of 54.26 and 54.26 from total of 141 samples. From the analysis of the data it is observed that the difference in the caste do not have much impact on the wage level but it is the sample size from each caste is determinant. There exist on an average a variation of ₹ 50-100 on different caste categories.

Table 20 Shows the Wage Differentials Based on the Caste of Labors

Categories		Daily Wage statistics (in Rs.)		
		Mean	Standard deviation	No of observation
ST	Natives	416.67	23.57	2
	Migrants	317.10	36.85	40
	ST Total	321.84	42.02	42
SC	Natives	427.78	47.14	9
	Migrants	321.08	31.93	112
	SC Total	329.01	43.38	121
OBC	Natives	409.19	41.77	61
	Migrants	326.71	51.57	159
	OBC Total	349.58	61.37	220
Others	Natives	429.86	54.26	49
	Migrants	319.93	54.26	92
	Others Total	358.14	68.55	141

(Source: Calculation using primary survey data)

➤ *Wage Categories Based on Level of Education of Labors*

On analyzing the wage difference among the natives and migrants based on the level of Education it has been observed that the educational level of the labors is not much a deterrent factor as most of them are engaged in low and semi-skilled sectors. The illiterate native on an average earn ₹ 438.89 whereas a migrant earn ₹ 310.85 with SD of 34.69 & 40.57 from total of 61 samples including both. Similarly in workers with primary education earns ₹ 411.67(natives) and ₹ 329.03 (migrants), with SD of 36.01 & 51.87 from total of 234 samples surveyed. Secondary level it is ₹ 420.22 (natives) and ₹ 319.93(migrants) with SD of 56.07 and 27.53 from 223 samples. The workers with educational qualification with graduation and above are very low to 6 samples comprising both the migrant and native population with an average earnings of ₹ 470.00(natives) and ₹ 283.33(migrants) with SD of 24.72 and 0.00 accordingly. This shows that the level of education does not have any direct effect on the wages earned, it is the skill and proficiency in the field, sector engaged and hours worked that matters the wage level.

Table 21 Shows the Category of Labors Based on Level of Education

Categories		Daily Wage statistics (in Rs.)		
		Mean	Standard deviation	No. of observation
illiterate	Natives	438.89	34.69	3
	Migrants	310.85	40.57	58
	illiterate Total	317.15	48.82	61
Primary	Natives	411.67	36.01	52
	Migrants	329.03	51.87	182
	Primary Total	347.39	59.66	234
Secondary	Natives	420.22	56.07	61
	Migrants	319.93	27.53	162
	Secondary Total	347.36	58.37	223
Graduation and above	Natives	470.00	24.72	5
	Migrants	283.33	0.00	1
	Graduates and above Total	438.89	79.35	6

(Source: Calculation using primary survey data)

CHAPTER FOUR FINDINGS AND CONCLUSION

This section of the report consist the major findings which have come up from the study, and various suggestions based on the findings and a conclusion on the internal migration to Kerala its trends, patterns and nature.

➤ *The Major Findings Of The Study Are*

- The migrant labor community comprise a major proportion of male population with 70% of unmarried men within an age group of 20-30 years (62%) followed by 30-40 years (22%) from (Table 3.1) and (Table 3.5).
- 58% of the migrant population are Hindus a mixed population from all the states followed 34% of Muslim proportion mainly from West Bengal and Bihar along with Bangladeshi illegal migrants and 6% of Christians who are usually from North East and Assam, rest of population other communities.
- The accommodation, toilet facility, working condition, drinking water facility are not satisfactory (Table 3.6, 3.7, and 3.8) shows it.
- The educational level of Migrant labors are too low and many are even illiterate (Table 3.4).
- West Bengal is the state with highest migrant population (42%) followed by Assam (17.37%) and Bihar being the third (16.63%) from (Table 3.9).
- Most of the migrant labors are working as daily labors (66%) and other on contract basis (33%) from (Table 3.10).
- On analyzing the remittance details 95% of the migrant labors remit money to their home state and among them 665 remit through friends and only 23 5 remit through banks which is been accounted properly.(Table 3.11 and 3.12).
- There exist wage differentials between the native and migrant workers, daily earnings for a native daily labor is ₹650-₹750, whereas that of a migrant labor is ₹350-₹500 daily.

From the results and findings emerged from the study, there is clearly a need to address the following problems to have a healthy and useful contribution by this migratory process:

- A compulsory registration of migrant labors to account the correct flow of migration including the personal and migratory details.
- Improving the housing and living conditions of the labors. The government officials should ensure that adequate facilities are provided by the employer or companies who hire the labors.
- Adoption of Social security measure like insurance, health cards, work card etc. and other credentials, which includes judicial services too.
- Establishing help centers similar to foreign embassies for international migrants to solve their problems on social, living and employment related issues.
- Measures to sustain good relation with the native population by migrant people as presently they being treated as a secondary citizens.
- Ensuring every migrant workers hired have Bank A/C, so that exact accounting of wage, remittance and money flow from the Kerala economy can be accounted.

CHAPTER FIVE CONCLUSION

Even though all these issues and problems were faced by them, most of them still wish to stay in Kerala as it is the place of virtue for them. Where they could earn more money, have good climate and good food. Even many complain that the Malayali community is good and behaves gently compared to the landlords and Zamindars of their region. Along with this, there exist a specified community who oppose this huge labor migration to Kerala by acquiring them as the carriers of infectious diseases, unhygienic community and reasons for the emergence of slums in Kerala. Many in turn acquire them for the increasing crimes in the state. But on examining the growth of Kerala GDP and the contribution of this in-migrant laborers in the growth of each sector especially in the unskilled labor sector where the state had faced a huge crisis over the past years is indispensable as now even the agriculture had also started in demanding them with the increasing shortage of labor for work.

The large-scale migration from all parts of the country to Kerala holds a true story of migrant's flows, a script replete with opportunities, exploitations, sacrifices, gains and hopes. A perfect plot of other state peoples who build up their edifices by the lives, contributions and atrocities of migrant laborers. While Kerala has the same replica treading its path called development in the cost of thousands of lives and their emotions, with a bad side of cultural divide. A state with better human indices and sensibilities. Migrant laborers in the state are not enjoying any protection under the labor laws of the central as well as the state. No appropriate welfare measures and to a minimum social security floor. One of the main constraints the state faces on the large-scale labor migration is framing policies for the migrant workers and their socio-economic concerns, due to the absence of authentic information and data on the existing and flowing migrant workers in the state. The people from different states with distinct culture and food habits migrated with the same motive. It would not be sufficient to think of migrant laborers as a single set without differing backgrounds and needs and a culturally sensitive intervention would be effective in understanding and formulating effective and necessary steps to maintain a healthy flow of migrant laborers to the state which is now a necessity to sustain Kerala's economic growth.

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MIGRATION SURVEY SCHEDULE

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A. Personal and Migration details

District Name				Block Name			
Name of the Village/town of Construction site				Name of the respondent			
Sector (Rural=1 and Urban=2)		Age (in years)		Sex (male=1 and female=2)			
Caste (ST=1, SC=2, OBC=3 and Others=4)		Marital Status (Unmarried=1, Married=2, Widow/Separated=3)			Level of education (illiterate=1, primary=2, Secondary=3, above=4)		
Religion (Hindu=1, Muslim=2, Christian=3, Others=4)		State of Domicile (Kerala=1 and others=2)			If state of domicile is not Kerala then Specify		
If Migrant then mention the period since migrated (in years) to Kerala		If Migrant: then no. of times visited home state (Since 1 st , June, 2015 to the date of survey)					
Through whom you have migrated to Kerala? (Contractors=1, Friends=2, Relatives=3, Own=4, others=5)		How many members are there in your family?	No. of Members by Sex:		Male	Female	
			Below 15 years Old				
			15 to 59 years Old				
			60 years and above				

Total land possession by your family		How many are the earning members in your family?		What is your relation to the head of your household? (self=1, Spouse=2, Married Son=3, Unmarried Son=4, Daughter=5, and others=6)	
Agricultural land (in Acres)		No. of Males Earners			
Residential land (in Square feet)		No. of Female Earners			
Age of household head (in years)	Sex of the household head(male=1 and female=2)	Level of education of household head(illiterate=1, primary=2, Secondary=3, above=4)		Occupation household head (Self-emp=1 and Casual labour=2, regular salaried worker=3)	
Details of households asset holdings (Approximate value in Rs.)					
Live Animals (Cows, Bullocks, Buffaloes, Goats, Hens etc.)		Durable Assets (TV, radio, Cycles, Motor bikes, Cars, ACs, Mobile phones etc.)		Financial Assets/savings (bonds, shares, LIC , Bank savings etc.)	

B. Employment And Wage Details

How many weeks did you spend for getting your employment in Kerala?		Did you get work regularly (all the 30 days in a month)? Yes=1 No=2		What is your last monthly income (in Rs.)?	
How many days did you work in last month?		Other than construction work what are the other type job you do?		What is your average daily earnings from other jobs (in Rs.)?	
Nature of employment (Permanent=1, Contract=2, Daily wage=3, Others=4)			Do you posses any bank account? (Yes=1, No=2)		
If yes, Type of Account Current A/C=1, SB=2 & others=3		Who buy an insurance for you?(Own=1, Family=2. Contractors=3, No Insurance=4)			
What type of accommodation you have? (Fully furnished Pucca=1, Only Pakka=2, Semi pakka/cemented=3, Kacha =4 & No house=5)					
What type of toilet use? (Private toilet within home=1, Public Toilet=2, No Toilet=3)		What type of water you drink? (Bottled/packed=1, , Tube well=2, Wells/ponds=3 Public water sources/tape water=4)			
What was your occupation before migration?		How much was your average Monthly earnings before migration?			
Sources and Amount of Family income (Rs):					
Farm Income		Wage Income		Land and Asset Income	Any other Income
What is your monthly Expenditure pattern? (in Rs)					

On Food Items	Expenses on Liquors, Soft drinks and other beverages	Expenses of Cinemas and other entertainments etc.	On Health care	House rent	Drinking water	Any other
Do you manage to generate any surplus income? <i>Yes=1 No=2</i>		If yes how much in the last year (in Rs)		Did you send any remittance to your family during the last year (<i>Yes=1 and No=2</i>)		
If yes how much did you remit during the last year (in Rs)			If yes how many times did you remit during the last year (Frequency)			
How do you send the money to your family? (<i>Banks=1, Post Office=2, Friends=3, Self=4, Others=5</i>)				Do you think that you are relatively better-off after migration? <i>Yes=1 No=2</i>		
If YES Why? Reasons						
If NO Why? Reasons						